

Trends in associated techniques for Pattern Recognition for the Classification of Hand Movements with Electromyography signals

Arly Dario Rincon-Quintero
Unidades Tecnológicas de Santander,
Colombia

ORCID: 0000-0002-4479-5613

Andrés Felipe Jiménez Quezada
Unidades Tecnológicas de Santander,
Colombia

ORCID: 0000-0003-1643-3073

Camilo Leonardo Sandoval-Rodriguez
Unidades Tecnológicas de Santander,
Colombia

ORCID: 0000-0001-8584-0137

Omar Lengerke
Unidades Tecnológicas de Santander,
Colombia

ORCID: 0000-0001-9360-7319

Nicole Andrea Castillo Zambrano
Unidades Tecnológicas de Santander,
Colombia

ORCID: 0000-0002-5456-9900

Carlos Andrés Angulo Julio
Unidades Tecnológicas de Santander,
Colombia

ORCID: 0000-0002-1159-2828

Abstract— This work presents a review to learn about the associated pattern recognition techniques for the classification of hand movements with Surface Electromyography (sEMG) signals. To find out which are the classifiers, the search criteria can be used through bibliometrics. The information was reviewed in the VOSviewer application, which was used in different bibliographic sources such as Web of Science, Scopus, and IEEE xplora. The words used were electromyography, classifiers, hand, and gesture. These data were analyzed and revealed different types of classifiers such as: Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), Support Vector Machine SVM, Convolutional Neuronal Networks (CNN), Artificial Neuronal Networks (ANN), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN). Each of the options was chosen by using it in the research, conducting the tests and scoring the average of acceptance or rejection. The results determine that the previous classifiers described represent an accuracy percentage greater than 90%, which means that they are suitable for performing this type of recognition.

Keywords — *Electromyography, classifiers, hand, gestures, LDA.*

I. Introduction

Electromyography (EMG) is a technique used to record and assess the electrical activity of muscles [1]. For the evaluation of neuromuscular diseases, EMG signal is widely used in diagnostic procedures [2]. On the other hand, the brain is responsible for sending electrical signals to the muscles to contract or relax them, thus allowing any movement type [3],[4]. It's also true that needles, wires, or probes are elements or methods used for sensing EMG signals.

The discovery of a muscle that generates electricity in electric stingrays aroused curiosity about the variety of signals involved in gestures [5], [6], and further interested researchers in hand gesture recognition using surface electromyography (sEMG) signals [7]–[11]. Movements or gesture recognition has different applications: treatment and diagnosis of pathologies and the design of functional prostheses.

sEMG signals are picked up by surface electrodes[10][12], which do not cause pain or skin discomfort compared to invasive needle-based sensors that penetrate the skin. However, these signals are dynamic and complex, which implies a series of difficulties when approaching their applications [13]. According to [14], the equipment design is not according to collect sEMG data on some parts of the body.

In many of the investigations related to sEMG signal processing, a series of stages is mentioned to improve the study of the characteristics. First, for data collection, it is necessary to perform pre-processing to reduce signal interference and to remove redundant channels through the variance theorem[14]. The processing shall use windowing strategies[4], [6], to ensure that the signal works in the time, frequency, or time-frequency domain. Finally, classifiers are used to help separate the characteristics of each hand gesture [7]-[9]. Here, a systematic search was carried out in some databases to be later analyzed in VOSviewer to identify some classifiers for hand movement recognition using sEMG signals.

II. Materials and methods

This research is based on the use of the VOSviewer application, a tool for the construction and visualization of bibliometric networks with information from some databases such as IEEE xplora, Scopus and Web of Science.

A network of keywords was made considering 92 outstanding documents generated from the Web of Science query with words such as Classifiers, Electromyography, Gestures and Hand, which were processed and analyzed in VOSviewer, Fig. 1 shows a network that is made up of 454 nodes, 28 groups and 4379 links. Its visualization was improved by parameterizing the software to determine the central bases, which are: gesture recognition (light blue), electromyography (dark blue) and classification (grey). The review of this work focused on the main concepts identified above, since they are mostly related to the set of other words. In addition, it was found that between 2018 and 2022 the most used classifiers were K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN), Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), Support Vector Machines (SVM), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and

Documents by subject area

Fig. 5. Percentages of documents according to their research areas.

In [23] was carried out the evaluation of the recognition of patterns for the decoding of movements. The offline and real-time performance of nine classification algorithms for ten different movements was studied. This evaluation showed that the LDA and MLE classifiers achieved an accuracy and completion rate greater than 68% and 69% respectively. Also, these two classifiers obtained the best offline accuracy with values of 97.9% (LDA) and 97.0% (MLE). Additionally, the classifier that required less time for training was MLE with 0.17 seconds. On the other hand, the percentages of precision in real-time were: MLP-69.8%, LDA-69.3% and MLE-68.4.

On the other hand, in [11] different classification techniques were evaluated running for several days. Specifically, these tests were performed for seven days and the proposed classifiers were LDA, ANN, SVM, KNN, TREE. The first days it did not show good results but as the days went by it improved. The comparative analysis showed that ANN and LDA were the most accurate.

The use of hybrid vectors generates good results in the classification, since they strengthen more information about the characteristics that highlight differences between the signals. Therefore, a good performance of sEMG classifiers depends largely on the stages of feature extraction and dimensionality reduction, since these are the phases that simplify the process, extracting relevant information from the signal [24].

IV. Conclusions

We review trends in techniques used for hand gesture recognition with sEMG signals. We use the VOSviewer application with different bibliographic sources to establish these research trends incorporating recognition of hand and wrist movement patterns. The analysis showed that publications on topics related to pattern recognition for hand movement classification, such as model training, machine learning, and myoelectric control, have increased rapidly over the past five years. The evolution of signal processing techniques has accompanied this development of knowledge.

The results show advances in the recognition of hand movement pattern driven by areas of knowledge associated with general engineering, computer science and medicine. Although this is not entirely surprising, it is striking that the contribution also comes from the clinical areas of medicine and reveals a considerable impact on the generation of applied knowledge.

On the other hand, different information processing techniques used to classify movements can be observed. Likewise, the growing number of studies associated with classifiers based on linear discriminant analysis (LDA) suggest that it has favorable results and high levels of accuracy in pattern recognition for movement identification compared to other techniques. Also, LDA showed good offline and real-time performance. In this way, open issues reveal future work on the hand movements classification in the time domain.

References

- [1] A. Waris, I. K. Niazi, M. Jamil, K. Englehart, W. Jensen, and E. N. Kamavuako, "Multiday evaluation of techniques for EMG-based classification of hand motions," *IEEE J. Biomed. Heal. Informatics*, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 1526–1534, 2018.
- [2] L. F. Bender, "Muscles alive: their functions revealed by electromyography," *JAMA*, vol. 201, no. 4, p. 277, 1967.
- [3] P. Kaczmarek, T. Mańkowski, and J. Tomczyński, "putEMG—a surface electromyography hand gesture recognition dataset," *Sensors*, vol. 19, no. 16, p. 3548, 2019.
- [4] C. L. S. Rodriguez, R. V. Mejia, B. E. T. Romero, A. D. R. Quintero, and A. J. R. Nieves, "Relationship between force signal and superficial electromyographic signals associated to hand movements," *Period. Eng. Nat. Sci.*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 64–73, 2023.
- [5] M. Wehner, "Man to machine, applications in electromyography," *EMG methods Eval. muscle nerve Funct.*, vol. 29, pp. 427–454, 2012.
- [6] M. B. I. Reaz, M. S. Hussain, and F. Mohd-Yasin, "Techniques of EMG signal analysis: detection, processing, classification and applications," *Biol. Proced. Online*, vol. 8, pp. 11–35, 2006.
- [7] A. Hartwell, "Machine learning for hand gesture classification from surface electromyography signals," University of Sheffield, 2019.
- [8] H. M. Pace Bedetti, "The effect of" Postural Freedom" in laparoscopic surgery," Universitat Politècnica de València, 2019.
- [9] S. Nebe *et al.*, "Enhancing Precision in Human Neuroscience," 2023.
- [10] M. A. Oskoei and H. Hu, "GA-based feature subset selection for myoelectric classification," in *2006 IEEE international conference on robotics and biomimetics*, 2006, pp. 1465–1470.
- [11] J. Kim, E. S. Gardinier, V. Vempala, and D. H. Gates, "The effect of powered ankle prostheses on muscle activity during walking," *J. Biomech.*, vol. 124, p. 110573, 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiomech.2021.110573>.
- [12] C. L. Sandoval-Rodriguez, A. C. Pita-Mejia, R. Villamizar-Mejia, B. E. Tarazona-Romero, and O. Lengerke-Perez, "Model to Relationship the Speed of Hand Movements with the SEMG Signals from the Forearm," in *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2022, vol. 2224, no. 1, p. 12094.
- [13] V. Alimisis, V. Mouzakis, G. Gennis, E. Tsouvalas, C. Dimas, and P. P. Sotiriadis, "A Hand Gesture Recognition Circuit Utilizing an Analog Voting Classifier," *Electronics*, vol. 11, no. 23, p. 3915, 2022.

- [14] B. Kundu and D. S. Naidu, "Classification and feature extraction of different hand movements from EMG signal using machine learning based algorithms," in *2021 International Conference on Electrical, Communication, and Computer Engineering (ICECCE)*, 2021, pp. 1–5.
- [15] L. A. Hidalgo Torres, Y. San Martin Reyes, and J. D. Chailloux Peguero, "Capture of the Voluntary Motor Intention from the Electromyography Signal," in *VIII Latin American Conference on Biomedical Engineering and XLII National Conference on Biomedical Engineering: Proceedings of CLAIB-CNIB 2019, October 2-5, 2019, Cancún, México*, 2020, pp. 28–36.
- [16] A. Ullah, S. Ali, I. Khan, M. A. Khan, and S. Faizullah, "Effect of analysis window and feature selection on classification of hand movements using EMG signal," in *Intelligent Systems and Applications: Proceedings of the 2020 Intelligent Systems Conference (IntelliSys) Volume 3*, 2020, pp. 400–415.
- [17] Y. Sun *et al.*, "Intelligent human computer interaction based on non redundant EMG signal," *Alexandria Eng. J.*, vol. 59, no. 3, pp. 1149–1157, 2020.
- [18] S. Abbaspour, A. Naber, M. Ortiz-Catalan, H. GholamHosseini, and M. Lindén, "Real-time and offline evaluation of myoelectric pattern recognition for the decoding of hand movements," *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 16, p. 5677, 2021.
- [19] K. Englehart, B. Hudgins, P. A. Parker, and M. Stevenson, "Classification of the myoelectric signal using time-frequency based representations," *Med. Eng. & Phys.*, vol. 21, no. 6–7, pp. 431–438, 1999.
- [20] E. Guzmán-Muñoz and G. Méndez-Rebolledo, "Electromyography in the rehabilitation sciences," *Rev. Salud Uninorte*, vol. 34, no. 3, pp. 753–765, 2018.
- [21] N. Özgören and S. Arıtan, "Peak counting in surface electromyography signals for quantification of muscle fatigue during dynamic contractions," *Med. Eng. Phys.*, vol. 107, p. 103844, 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.medengphy.2022.103844>.
- [22] J. Tu, Z. Dai, X. Zhao, and Z. Huang, "Lower limb motion recognition based on surface electromyography," *Biomed. Signal Process. Control*, vol. 81, p. 104443, 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bspc.2022.104443>.
- [23] J. Yoo *et al.*, "Residual one-dimensional convolutional neural network for neuromuscular disorder classification from needle electromyography signals with explainability," *Comput. Methods Programs Biomed.*, vol. 226, 2022, doi: [10.1016/j.cmpb.2022.107079](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmpb.2022.107079).
- [24] M. A. Ozdemir, D. H. Kisa, O. Guren, and A. Akan, "Dataset for multi-channel surface electromyography (sEMG) signals of hand gestures," *Data Br.*, vol. 41, p. 107921, 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2022.107921>.